

Milestone: MS28 - Initial set of recommendations for addressing use cases

Lead Participant: SC

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Due: September 2024

Date Of Completion: November 2024

Means of Verification

- Deliverable 7.5
(<https://zenodo.org/records/14537083>)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, to finish D7.5

Project participants & others

SC, BSC, Erasmus MC, UNISR, ELIXIR Hub, HSR, UT

Next action steps

- Finalise user journeys and stories
- Transfer user journeys to Pillar II in order to identify technical requirements (mapping the functionalities with the GDI products) and identify gaps in the GDI infrastructure
- Transfer user journeys to Pillar I to ensure the legal coverage

